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Silent Boundaries: Exploring the Limits of Legal Confidentiality in Poland

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Legal confidentiality, an integral aspect of European legal culture and legal services, plays a pivotal role in safeguarding the trust and privacy of professional-client relationships. This study focuses on the multifaceted dimensions of legal secrecy, particularly within the context of commercial lawyers in the European legal services market, using Polish legal advisers as an exemplar. The research explores evolving attitudes, expectations, and perceptions of legal secrecy amidst dynamic legal changes and discrepancies in interpretations among lawyers, public authorities, and citizens.

A comprehensive mixed-method approach was used, including surveys, structured in-depth interviews, content analysis, and desk research, to investigate the diverse facets of legal secrecy. Findings reveal that while legal secrecy remains highly esteemed, its interpretation varies significantly across national and EU laws and among stakeholders. There are a multitude of types of legal secrecy, creating confusion and opportunities for public authorities to breach confidentiality.

The study underscores the critical need for standardization and unification of legal secrecy across European countries to enhance cross-border legal services, streamline justice systems, and bolster citizen protection. It emphasizes that despite legal and societal changes, the fundamental essence and importance of legal secrecy in upholding democracy, justice, and trust remain steadfast.

Keywords: Legal Secrecy; Legal Confidentiality; European Legal Services; Cross-border Legal Services; Legal service management, Professional Services, Marketing of services, EU law; Polish law; lawyers; Mixed Methods; Legal Profession; Sociology of Law

Introduction

Confidentiality is vital for the legal profession and the judiciary, embodying a principle of paramount importance. In Poland, the application of confidentiality within legal practice is multifaceted, particularly for regulated professions such as advocates or legal advisers (in Poland, also called attorneys-at-law). This principle is incompatible with its public trust role and a long-standing tradition of advocacy aimed at protecting individuals from state overreach. Absolute discretion in matters entrusted to lawyers is essential, ensuring that sensitive information remains shielded from state authorities. Confidentiality thus becomes a bulwark against intrusive state power, preserving the independence of legal practitioners and the integrity of attorney-client relationships (read more: Marchwicki, 2015).

European culture, tradition, and social norms deeply respect the ethos of legal confidentiality, with its principles being integral to the delivery of legal services throughout Europe. Both national and EU law meticulously define and uphold these standards, with courts at both levels acting as vigilant guardians of confidentiality norms (Eva, 2015, pp. 33–37; Gerven, 2013, pp. 1–18).

Beyond general professional secrecy, legal confidentiality encompasses a broader obligation. Specifically, it requires professionals such as lawyers to protect client information, thus fortifying the trust and privacy fundamentals of the professional-client relationship (Auburn, 2000, pp. 1–13, 57–69).

Contrary to prevailing assumptions, the scope and application of professional confidentiality differ markedly between professions. Lawyers, for instance, are bound by a more expansive confidentiality obligation that covers all client-related information, regardless of its source. This contrasts with the narrower scope of accountants, limited to information obtained during accounting services (Desai, 2013; Goldfarb, 2009, pp. 164–166). Furthermore, lawyers' confidentiality obligations are underpinned by both legal and ethical grounds, while accountants' obligations are primarily ethical and subject to variation based on jurisdiction (Kędziera, 2017, pp. 34–41).

The mechanisms for disclosing information protected under attorney-client confidentiality are often defined by law. A growing body of national and EU legislation delineates conditions under which legal confidentiality may be waived or disclosed, raising concerns about the erosion of this fundamental principle. Generally, lawyers and citizens are hesitant to disclose confidential information, except under stringent legal procedures, particularly in matters of grave concern like terrorism or money laundering.

This cautious stance is also evident in reactions to attempts by state agencies to access confidential information, often met with significant resistance from both legal professionals and the public.

Poland is an interesting example of legal services market and is particularly suitable for the focus of the study. What is unique is the existence of two legal professions - legal advisers (attorney at law, “radcowie prawni”) and advocates (“adwokaci”) - with distinct historical origins although currently with very similar entitlements. These professions are governed by separate professional bodies and are regulated by different legal frameworks (Radcowie Prawni, 1982; Adwokatura, 1982). Legal advisers are traditionally associated (perhaps unjustly) with commercial law, in contrast to advocates who are more commonly linked with criminal law. However, in practice, both legal advisers and advocates handle the same types of cases in the market. In this study, we focus on legal advisers as representative of the legal profession in Poland. Nevertheless, the findings of this study can be extrapolated to encompass advocates as well.

This study aims to **dissect the role of confidentiality in the practice of commercial lawyers**, with a focus on Polish legal advisers (attorneys-at-law) within the European legal market. It seeks to ascertain the value clients place on legal confidentiality and under what circumstances lawyers and clients consent to disclosure. Additionally, the study aims to **categorise and analyse various types of confidentiality in legal practice**, gauging their perception by clients and the wider society. The ultimate goal is to recommend harmonised standards for waiving confidentiality, aligning client expectations with legal norms and lawyer ethics.

The research hypothesis posits that **perceptions and attitudes toward legal confidentiality among lawyers, clients, and public authorities are evolving in response to dynamic legal landscapes**. There is a discernible disconnect between these perceptions and the standards set by EU, national, and corporate law, especially regarding deontological norms for legal advisers.

Confidentiality in Legal Practice: Polish Law in the European Context

Poland's legal system, balancing its EU membership and post-soviet heritage, offers a unique perspective on legal confidentiality. The interplay of EU law and historical influences creates a complex backdrop for legal practitioners, combining modern legal standards with challenges rooted in the nation's past.

The Polish legal landscape features two main legal professions: advocates (*adwokat*) and legal advisers (also called attorney-at-law, *radca prawny*) (Wojciech M. Jakubowski, 1997, pp. 74–78). However, governed by respective legal statutes, in practice almost identical, these roles highlight the importance of confidentiality in maintaining ethical and client-focused legal practices (Białkowska, 2021, pp. 79–102; Gerven, 2013, pp. 2–23).

Polish law recognises various types of legal confidentiality, each governed by specific statutes and ethical codes. These include professional confidentiality, defensive confidentiality, business confidentiality, and other forms that address the diverse needs of legal practice.

Legal Professional Privilege

Under Polish law, the concept of legal professional privilege, also known as legal confidentiality, is a fundamental aspect of legal practice. This privilege is enshrined in the Act on Legal Advisers (Article 3) (Radcowie Prawni, 1982) and the Act on Advocates (Article 6) (Adwokatura, 1982), which apply similarly to Polish legal advisers, advocates, and foreign lawyers practising in Poland.

Legal advisers in Poland are bound by a comprehensive duty of confidentiality. They are required to keep secret all information learnt in connection with providing legal assistance. This obligation extends to various relationships, encompassing interactions between the legal adviser and the client, the legal adviser and external entities, and even between the legal adviser or the client and state institutions.

The principles of confidentiality are further detailed in the Code of Ethics of Attorneys at Law, particularly in Articles 15 to 24 (KERP, 2023). Here, the National Bar of Attorneys-at-Law outlines the methods and principles for upholding legal professional privilege. Non-compliance with these rules can lead to disciplinary liability for legal advisers.

The critical aspect of the Polish confidentiality law is its universal application. Article 22 of the Code of Ethics of Attorneys at Law highlights that confidentiality obligations also extend to associates, illustrating the principle of universal confidentiality. This means that not only lawyers, but also their trainees, clients, colleagues, prosecutors, and others who possess confidential information are bound by these confidentiality rules.

Although advocates in Poland are subject to confidentiality rules similar to those of legal advisers, the normative foundations for these rules differ (Skuczyński, 2016, pp.

247–285). Advocates must adhere to analogous obligations as set out in their respective legal statutes and ethical guidelines.

The legal framework in Poland establishes a rigorous and expansive approach to professional legal privilege, underscoring the importance of confidentiality in various aspects of legal practice. Both legal advisers and advocates, along with related parties, are included within this framework, ensuring the protection of confidential information throughout the legal profession.

Defensive Confidentiality

Defensive confidentiality (defending counsel's secret) is a specific type of confidentiality that is applied exclusively to criminal proceedings under Polish law. Defined in Article 178 of the Code of Criminal Procedure (K. p. k., 1997), it protects legal advisers, advocates, and even foreign lawyers practising in Poland from being compelled to testify about information obtained through legal counselling or case management. This form of confidentiality is particularly robust, offering, by its nature, no exceptions for disclosure under any circumstances. The limited possibilities of its waiver and information disclosure are explained in the following sections.

The scope of defensive confidentiality (defending counsel's secret) is comprehensive. It not only prevents lawyers from being questioned as witnesses in criminal trials but also extends to all documents and evidence they may produce or possess during defence activities. Additionally, this protection isn't limited to lawyers alone; trainees and associates involved in the case are also covered under this confidentiality (Patyra, 2018, pp. 14–22).

Despite the strong protection offered by defensive confidentiality, there is an ongoing debate in both Poland and the European Union about the evolving nature of legal confidentiality in response to changing legal and social needs (read more: Winter et al., 2020). Although defensive confidentiality is supposedly absolute, the line between this type of confidentiality and legal professional privilege is fuzzy and raises complex issues. These are discussed in more detail in the following sections of the article.

Business Confidentiality

Business confidentiality, or trade secret, is a vital aspect for legal advisers and advocates in the realm of legal practice in Poland. As entrepreneurs managing their law

firms, these professionals are legally entitled to protect the confidential aspects of their business operations.

This type of confidentiality is anchored in Polish legislation by Article 11 of the Act on Counteracting Unfair Competition (U. o. k. i k., 2007). This specific article outlines the parameters within which legal firms can protect sensitive information, such as strategic business methods, client databases, and internal operational details, from unauthorised disclosure.

On the European front, the protection of business confidentiality is further reinforced by relevant EU directive (Directive (EU) 2016/943, 2016). This directive establish a unified framework across EU member states, ensuring a consistent approach to handling and protecting trade secrets, thereby aligning Poland's national laws with broader European standards.

A key consideration in the context of business confidentiality is the legal implications of its breach. Infringing these confidentiality rules can have significant consequences under both criminal and civil law. Such legal accountability highlights the critical importance placed on maintaining the integrity of trade secrets, not just for the individual law firm's competitive advantage, but also for upholding the legal standards set forth by Polish and EU legislation.

Additional Forms of Legal Confidentiality

Lawyers also encounter other forms of confidentiality. Additional confidentiality forms in Polish law include:

- Preliminary Criminal Proceedings: Governed by Article 241 of the Polish Code of Criminal Procedure (K. p. k., 1997).
- In-Camera Hearings: Addressed in Article 360 of the Polish Code of Criminal Procedure (K. p. k., 1997).
- Mediator Confidentiality: Defined in Article 178a of the Polish Code of Criminal Procedure (K. p. k., 1997).
- Negotiation confidentiality: Stipulated by Article 72¹ of the Polish Civil Code (K. c., 1964).
- Classified information: Specified in the Law on Protection of Classified Information (Informacje Niejawne, 2010).

Legal professionals must adhere to these confidentiality rules, depending on the context and nature of their legal work (Borzemski et al., 2022; examples may be found: Rusinek, 2007).

Information Disclosure and Waiver Procedures

The disclosure of confidential information and the conditions under which public authorities can waive confidentiality are critical issues for lawyers. The state and supra-state authorities, including those of the European Union, often engage in practices that significantly impact legal confidentiality. One of the most pressing challenges is the tension between defensive confidentiality and legal professional privilege. Defensive confidentiality is sometimes conflated with legal professional privilege by prosecutors' offices and courts, leading to complex legal disputes (*CCBE Report*, 2023).

Legal professional privilege in Poland, as governed for attorneys-at-law is not absolute (Auburn, 2000, pp. 79–99, 195–261; Gerven, 2013, pp. 13–21). This statute specifies exceptions, particularly in cases involving money laundering, terrorist financing, and issues related to the protection of EU financial interests, as dictated by regulations from the European Public Prosecutor's Office. These exceptions reflect the influence of EU law on national legal standards (Bachmaier, 2018, pp. 179–253; Gałęski & Zawłocki, 2019, pp. 5–19; Regulation No 17, 1962).

Furthermore, even within criminal proceedings, Polish law (as indicated by Article 180 of the Code of Criminal Procedure) allows exemptions from legal professional privilege in the interest of public welfare (Zagrodnik, 2020, pp. 83–108). This situation parallels the confidentiality concerns in trade secrets and the protection of classified information, where legal boundaries are frequently tested and redefined (Wils, 2019, pp. 25–39).

The ambiguity and overlap among different forms of confidentiality, including defensive confidentiality, legal professional privilege, trade secrets, and the protection of classified information, create a complex environment for legal practitioners. This complexity is often mirrored in the judiciary, and judges and prosecutors navigate these nuanced distinctions. Consequently, the rules governing the revocation or waiver of confidential information remain a subject of ongoing legal debate and controversy in Poland.

EU Regulations and Polish Legal Confidentiality

Entwined with the threads of European Union directives, the concept of legal confidentiality takes on a nuanced form, especially for Polish lawyers. This evolving landscape is marked by key EU regulations and law implementation procedures that intertwine with national legal practices, creating a unique dynamic for legal professionals in Poland.

The pivot point comes with the EU Council's regulation on EU financial interests, notably encapsulated in Article 20 (Regulation No 17, 1962). This provision opens the door for a nuanced approach to legal confidentiality, allowing partial waivers in specific circumstances, particularly concerning the Union's financial interests. For Polish lawyers, this represents a delicate balance between adhering to traditional professional privileges and aligning with broader EU financial security measures (Bachmaier, 2018, pp. 235–265).

When it comes to combating money laundering and terrorist activities, the EU directive on ushers in a new era of compliance for Polish legal practitioners (Directive (EU) 2015/849, 2021; Siclari, 2016, pp. 45–57). This directive not only mandates heightened vigilance, but also imposes responsibilities that may sometimes edge into the realm of traditional client-lawyer confidentiality. From reporting suspicious financial transactions to navigating asset seizures, Polish lawyers are at the crossroads of ethical practice and regulatory compliance (Stankiewicz & Pawełczyk, 2018, pp. 139–159; Stecyk, 2017, pp. 469–491).

The Court of Justice of the European Union emerges as a guiding beacon in this complex legal environment. Its role in interpreting EU regulations provides clarity and direction, particularly in delineating the extent to which lawyer independence can be balanced against pressing EU concerns like financial security and public safety (González-Díaz & Stuart, 2017, pp. 56–65; Sturli & Henry, 2023, pp. 165–167; Weiss, 2015, pp. 79–88).

In the midst of these regulations, the EU framework does not lose sight of the fundamental principles of lawyer autonomy and client confidentiality. The provision for legal appeals and the requirement for court authorisation before any breach of confidentiality offer reassurance. These safeguards ensure that Polish lawyers, while navigating the demands of EU law, retain the essence of their professional ethos and the trust of their clients.

Fluidity of Polish Legal Practice

In the Polish legal context, this fluidity is particularly evident. The behaviour of lawyers in Poland is not only a function of legal doctrine but is also deeply intertwined with economic and marketing dynamics. Their professional activities exemplify the concept of law in action - a principle that law is created and continually reshaped by social and economic realities, including the impact of existing norms on society.

Focussing on confidentiality in legal practice, the study recognises that its manifestations extend beyond the written statutes. In Poland, the existence, evolution, and application of confidentiality norms are social facts, intrinsically linked to social activity and market principles. The market reality faced by Polish lawyers presents a spectrum of issues that existing legal regulations may not fully encompass or address. This disparity highlights the inadequacy of current legal frameworks in responding to the dynamic social and economic landscape.

Therefore, a comprehensive understanding of the legal profession in Poland requires active and realistic monitoring of current phenomena, going beyond a mere analysis of existing legal rules. Observing the „living law” in action, especially in the context of social and economic changes in the Polish legal system, is crucial. This observation facilitates a deeper understanding of the empirical realities of legal practice and offers valuable insights for future recommendations for legal professionals.

The choice to base this study on sociological-economic-legal schools and paradigms is particularly pertinent. It aligns with the need to explore and understand the multifaceted nature of legal phenomena in Poland, where law, society, and economy are inextricably linked.

Study Methodology

This research is firmly grounded in the philosophical traditions of the Scandinavian school of legal realism and the Chicago school of law, supplemented by the paradigm of economic analysis of law. Influential scholars such as Axel Hägerström (Mindus, 2009) and Roscoe Pound (Pound, 1910) have primarily guided the sociological-economic-legal aspect of this research, while the economic dimension draws inspiration from Gary Becker and Richard Posner (Becker, 1968; Posner, 2014). These foundational perspectives underscore that legal phenomena are not static but fluid, significantly influenced by social factors.

Mixed Methods Research Approach

The study employs a triangulated research methodology, combining different methods to enhance the depth and breadth of the findings (developed and applied based on: Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2008). The study's design reflected a deep commitment to capturing the nuances of the legal landscape, drawing from a diverse participant base and employing varied research techniques.

(1) Dual Survey Approach (based on: Saris & Gallhofer, 2014)

- **Survey among the general public:** Using the SurvGo online research panel (*SurvGo*, 2023), we engaged with a broad spectrum of the Polish population, randomly drawing participants from a vast pool of 150,000 members. This approach ensured a representative sample of over 600 individuals, providing information on public perception with a 95% confidence level and a 3% sampling error.
- **Survey among legal professionals:** Turning our focus to the practitioners themselves, we reached out to Polish legal advisers and trainee legal advisers through an electronic survey. Using the extensive network of the bar association, we achieved an impressive response from 782 professionals out of a potential of 57,192 (established based on: *Rejestr Radców*, 2023), enriching our data with their first-hand experiences.

(2) Deepening the understanding: Semi-Structured Interviews (based on: Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009)

In parallel, we conducted 26 in-depth, semi-structured interviews with legal advisers and trainees. These face-to-face encounters, which spanned June 2018 to June 2022, were recorded and analysed. The consent of each participant added an ethical layer to our research, while the inductive approach to categorisation and coding unearthed rich, meaningful narratives.

(3) Complementing with Desk Research (Elo & Kyngäs, 2008)

To add depth to our empirical findings, we turned to desk research, dissecting legislative acts and legal applications through a lens of functional analysis (Kędzierski, 2018, pp. 34–46). This part of our research journey emphasised legal comparativism and

historical perspectives, further enriched by insights from other scientific studies and the literature.

Data Collection and Analysis Procedures

In conducting the survey, we used a purposeful selection strategy, ensuring that the participants were specifically relevant to our research objectives. The data collected from this process were then processed and compiled using the advanced capabilities of MaxQDA 2022 software (*MaxQDA*, 2022). This software facilitated a comprehensive and nuanced analysis of the survey responses, allowing a detailed exploration of the data.

The semi-structured interviews, integral to our study, mirrored the themes and questions of the survey conducted with legal advisers and trainees. Conducted face-to-face by our dedicated research team, these interviews offered a deeper and more personal insight into the subjects at hand. Each interview was recorded with the explicit consent of the participants, according to ethical research standards.

During the analysis phase, the categorisation and coding of the interview data were executed in several stages. The initial categorisation was performed *in vivo*, ensuring that the data's accuracy and richness were preserved. Our approach was inductively driven, focussing on deriving meaning and significance from the data. This methodological choice meant that any non-meaningful or irrelevant messages were deliberately omitted, sharpening the focus on the most pertinent and insightful data.

The entire study was conducted under the joint supervision of our research team and representatives of the National Bar Council of Attorneys-at-Law. This collaborative supervision ensured that the study adhered to both academic rigour and the professional standards expected by the legal community. The Council's agreement to use these materials for the current partial report further underscores the relevance and applicability to the Polish legal context.

The culmination of our methodological expedition is detailed in the comprehensive research report (Lipiec et al., 2022). This collaborative effort has led to a report that not only lays out our methods and findings, but also opens doors for future explorations in the dynamic field of legal practice.

Confidentiality in Polish Legal Practice: Empirical Study's Findings

The research has uncovered a pronounced disparity between the theoretical frameworks of legal confidentiality (law on the books) and its practical implementation in Poland.

Lawyers and their clients often navigate a landscape markedly different from the structured environment of legal regulations, revealing a significant gap between normative expectations and actual market practices.

Lawyer's Perspective

The most lawyers do not distinctly differentiate between legal professional privilege and other forms of confidentiality, such as defending counsel's secret. There appears to be a common confusion, leading to an overarching emphasis on maintaining lawyer-client confidentiality.

Figure 1 Lawyer-Recognised Legal Confidentiality Types (question: What form of secrecy do you consider legal confidentiality): Lawyer's Interview Data Insights (rate of

Regarding trade secrets and negotiation confidentiality, lawyers understand these as separate entities from professional privilege. However, the concept of trade secrets, particularly in the context of a law firm, is not often highlighted in their responses. Lawyers associate trade secrets with the technical, organisational and financial elements of a law firm, which contrasts with the substance-related aspects covered by professional privilege. For example, a legal adviser from Stalowa Wola noted:

We [...] have sources of client acquisition that are our secrets, company secrets, so I would not like to disclose that [...]. I will not comment on that because it is a trade secret. The settlements with clients, the issues of money and remuneration are the secret of my law firm, I don't talk to anyone about that.

Furthermore, the concept of negotiation confidentiality is acknowledged, particularly underlined by a Kraków legal adviser. This form of confidentiality requires legal advisers to maintain confidentiality during negotiations. However, there is an indication that the practice of maintaining negotiation confidentiality is not consistently upheld within the legal community (Chrobot, 2014):

We follow certain rules, e.g. the negotiation confidentiality. We have beautiful provisions in the legal adviser's code of ethics: negotiations are secret, and professional attorneys should not disclose information about them in the course of court proceedings. However, these are rather dead rules.

The study also highlights the widespread confusion that arises from the multiplicity of confidentiality forms. Many legal professionals expressed difficulty in navigating and complying with the various types of confidentiality, emphasising the practical challenges that this poses. This situation underscores the need for a more streamlined and harmonised approach to confidentiality rules, simplifying adherence, and improving understanding among legal practitioners.

Clients' Perspective

Investigating client perceptions of confidentiality within the Polish legal sphere unveils a nuanced picture, marked by a blend of awareness and uncertainty. This insight into the layperson's understanding offers a unique window into the complexities of legal confidentiality as it is experienced outside the professional realm.

When ordinary individuals engage with legal services, their familiarity with terms such as 'defending counsel's confidentiality,' 'professional privilege,' and 'trade secrets' is often superficial. This limited depth of understanding is reflective of their general distance from the legal world's complexities. As a result, various types of confidentiality coalesce in the public mind into a singular and overarching concept of legal confidentiality.

This confluence of different types of confidentiality into one generalised idea in public perception underscores a broader societal trend. It highlights a disconnect between the detailed and specific roles of legal professionals and the more general understanding held by those outside the legal profession.

From this societal point of view, there is an evident hierarchy in the recognition of confidentiality types. Professional privilege, often linked to the high-stakes environment of criminal law, is more familiar to the public. On the other hand, trade secrets are rarely associated with the legal profession, indicating a lack of public awareness of lawyers as business professionals.

Figure 2 Client-Recognised Types of Legal Confidentiality (question: Are you familiar with the mentioned form of legal secrecy): Client's Survey Data Analysis (rate of all responses, n=600 people).

This disparity in understanding raises an important issue: While the principle of legal confidentiality is universally upheld as crucial, its various forms do not enjoy equal understanding or respect among the general populace.

The findings advocate for a transformation towards a more streamlined and coherent legal framework regarding confidentiality. Simplifying the legal nuances surrounding confidentiality could significantly improve public understanding, fostering clearer and more effective interactions between clients and legal professionals.

This study highlights a crucial requirement within the Polish legal system: the need to demystify legal jargon and processes for the lay person. By closing the knowledge gap through educational initiatives and legal reforms, the legal system can become more approachable and comprehensible to those it aims to serve.

Confidentiality as a Core Value

Confidentiality transcends the mere professional obligation for Polish lawyers; it is a fundamental value intrinsic to their work and the justice system. The idea of practising law without the assurance of maintaining client confidentiality is inconceivable for them. Any breach of confidentiality, whether sanctioned by legal authority or accidental, is viewed not just as a professional lapse but as a transgression against the very essence of legal practice. This sentiment is prevalent regardless of the positions held by public authorities, clients, or bar associations. Confidentiality is upheld as a cornerstone for individual jurists, the broader legal establishment, and indeed, the entire Polish and European legal cultural framework.

Figure 3 Relevance of Lawyer Confidentiality (question: how important legal confidentiality is to you): Client's Survey Findings (rate of all responses, n=600 people).

Some legal advisers go beyond mere adherence to confidentiality; they actively engage in initiatives spearheaded by the Polish bar associations of advocates and attorneys at law and the Council of Bars and Law Societies of Europe (CCBE). Their aim is to establish a uniform standard of confidentiality across European bar associations (Dal, 2013, pp. 24–28; Mrowicki, 2019). These efforts underscore the belief that confidentiality is not just a protective measure for client interests, but a sacred trust. A Wroclaw legal adviser eloquently articulates this sentiment.

Professional privilege, the most important thing for lawyers and the justice system. Confidentiality extends beyond what the client reveals to the lawyer; it also encompasses what the lawyer learns from third parties, like the client's sister. Even what the client learns from the lawyer falls under the ambit of confidentiality. This was not always the case, as seen in the 2007 Code of Ethics for Legal Advisers (KERP, 2007), but it is a principle now widely acknowledged and respected across various European bar associations.

Clients, too, attribute immense value to legal confidentiality, viewing it as an integral part of their interactions with the legal system. A significant majority, 73%, expresses that they cannot envisage a just legal system or effective cooperation with legal professionals in the absence of confidentiality. This perspective is not limited to the lawyer-client relationship, but extends to the broader concept of legal services. Clients believe that confidentiality should be equally upheld by lawyers, themselves, and all involved in the legal aid process. Only a minimal fraction, 1%, deems confidentiality as non-essential, underscoring its widespread acceptance and importance as a foundational element of the legal state.

The study reveals that confidentiality is not merely a legal requirement in Poland but a deeply ingrained cultural and ethical norm, valued equally by legal professionals and their clients. This shared understanding underscores the need for a robust and universally accepted confidentiality framework, which improves trust and integrity within the Polish legal system.

The Complexity of Confidentiality Disclosure

The sanctity of legal confidentiality is deeply valued by individual lawyers, bar associations, and citizens alike in the Polish legal context. This reverence for confidentiality permeates through the legal system, shaping attitudes and practices related to its disclosure or waiver.

For most Polish legal advisers, the idea of revoking or disclosing legal secrets is fundamentally opposed, regardless of the circumstances. They uphold the principle that confidentiality, once bestowed, remains inviolate, a stance that often extends beyond the remit of public authority consent. Many legal professionals firmly believe that confidentiality should not be compromised, even with the sanction of courts, prosecutor's offices, or administrative bodies. In their view, confidentiality transcends

state institutions, representing a principle that exists independently of legal or governmental directives.

Figure 4 Citizen-Justified Legal Confidentiality Waivers (question: Do lawyers' clients accept the waiver of confidentiality, if so by whom): Client's Survey Insights (absolute indications, n=600 people).

This strong stance is further evidenced by their disapproval of disclosing confidential matters within social circles. Discussions of confidential issues with colleagues, acquaintances, or family members are considered unacceptable, highlighting the sacrosanct nature of confidentiality between the attorney and the client.

However, nuances exist in this otherwise rigid perspective. Some lawyers acknowledge scenarios where confidentiality might be more flexibly approached, particularly at the client's behest. In these instances, confidentiality is seen as a right belonging to the client, which they may choose to waive. This viewpoint is not universally held, but it is a notable perspective within the legal community (Warylewski, 2015, pp. 7–13; Żaczkiewicz-Zborska, 2019). Legal adviser from Szczecin in this manner summarises this approach:

Well, you see, in our profession, the sanctity of attorney-client confidentiality is paramount. For most of us, the idea of revoking or revealing legal secrets is completely out of the question, no matter the situation. This isn't just a professional duty; it is a core value. Once confidentiality is bestowed, it becomes inviolable. Our stance often goes beyond what is required by public authority consent.

Even if courts, prosecutor's offices, or administrative bodies give their approval, we believe that confidentiality should never be compromised. For us, it transcends the reach of state institutions. It is a principle that stands on its own, independent of any governmental directives.

And it is not just about official settings. We also firmly believe that confidential matters should not be discussed outside the professional sphere. Sharing confidential information with colleagues, friends, or family is considered unacceptable. It is about maintaining an unbreakable trust between the attorney and the client. So, in essence, our commitment to confidentiality is absolute.

In other legally specified situations, the willingness to disclose confidential information is somewhat more moderate. Lawyers recognise that, in certain critical cases, the disclosure of secrets might be warranted, though such instances are approached with caution and deliberation.

A developing trend in the legal market is the rise of comprehensive services, where legal advice is integrated with other professional inputs like detective work or psychological consultation. Despite the growing popularity of such multidisciplinary approaches, there is observable hesitance among lawyers to share confidential information with professionals outside the legal field. This reluctance presents a challenge in effectively handling complex cases that require a multifaceted approach. However, as these comprehensive services become more prevalent, there might be a gradual shift in attitudes, particularly when collaboration involves professionals such as physicians, psychologists, or mediators, who also place a high premium on confidentiality (Marchwicki, 2015, pp. 177–199). A German-Polish legal adviser and Rechtsanwalt from Zielona Góra, during the conversation, notes the problem of confidentiality when combining professional services:

Researcher: *With legal services now merging with other fields like detective work and psychology, how are lawyers feeling about confidentiality?*

Lawyer: Well, it is quite a balancing act. We see the potential in these combined services, but there is a real concern about sharing sensitive info with non-lawyers. Even so, as we collaborate more with professionals who also value privacy, such as doctors and psychologists, our outlook is gradually shifting. It is about finding that sweet spot, maintaining client trust while leveraging these innovative approaches.

The Polish legal system displays deep-seated respect for confidentiality, viewed as a cornerstone of the profession and legal practice. While there are instances where flexibility in handling confidentiality is acknowledged, these are approached with caution, reflecting the overarching principle that confidentiality is a fundamental, almost sacred aspect of legal practice.

Disclosure of Confidentiality in Judicial Context

Legal confidentiality, deeply entrenched in the legal framework, is subject to specific provisions that dictate its handling. Crucial among these are the guidelines outlining under what circumstances and in what manner confidentiality can be disclosed or waived in judicial and law enforcement contexts (subject in different settings: Auburn, 2000, pp. 79–99, 195–261; Borzowski et al., 2022, pp. 37–44, 60–63, 86–91; Rusinek, 2007, pp. 106–173). Lawyers and citizens generally consent to the revocation of legal secrets after a formal court decision. This respect for the judiciary's authority is predicated on the finality and legal binding nature of such rulings. Lawyers, particularly, show reluctance to disclose confidential information unless sanctioned by a final court decision. This respect for the judiciary's determinations reflects a broader societal and professional trust in the court's judgment.

However, the stance toward other arms of the legal system, such as preliminary criminal proceedings and executive authorities like the prosecutor's office, is markedly different. Both lawyers and clients exhibit strong resistance to the intrusion of these entities into matters protected by confidentiality. This opposition is rooted not only in a mistrust of the executive's power but also in a longstanding tradition of upholding lawyer-client privilege against authoritative overreach. The legal community advocates that any prosecutorial attempts to breach confidentiality must be rigorously contested in court and reported to bar associations (Pietrzak, 2019, pp. 94–97).

	Category	<i>Entities whose consent allows lawyers to disclose confidentiality</i>				
		None	Court	Client	Lawyer himself	Bar
Age	below 30	3.97%	25.83%	26.49%	17.22%	26.49%
	31-40	4.66%	27.68%	28.72%	16.69%	22.25%
	41-50	3.47%	29.46%	24.26%	18.81%	24.01%
	51-60	3.59%	34.13%	24.55%	15.57%	22.16%
	61-70	1.67%	30.00%	28.33%	18.33%	21.67%
	above 70	0	28.57%	23.81%	14.29%	33.33%
Experience	below 10	5.02%	28.15%	27.91%	16.16%	22.77%
	11-20	2.44%	28.31%	26.48%	19.14%	23.63%
	21-30	4.44%	31.67%	23.33%	17.22%	23.33%
	31-40	3.33%	30.00%	26.67%	16.67%	23.33%
	above 40	0	32.14%	25.00%	14.29%	28.57%
City Size	village	7.14%	21.43%	28.57%	14.29%	28.57%
	town, less than 50 000	2.72%	28.57%	27.21%	18.37%	23.13%
	town 50 000-100 000	2.36%	25.98%	26.77%	15.75%	29.13%
	city 100 000-500 000	3.33%	30.30%	27.27%	15.45%	23.64%
	city more than 500 000	4.59%	28.71%	26.62%	17.85%	22.23%
Firm Status	sole trader	3.88%	29.20%	26.69%	16.79%	23.43%
	co-partnership-big	3.77%	26.42%	24.53%	26.42%	18.87%
	co-partnership-medium	4.00%	28.00%	27.20%	17.60%	23.20%
	co-partnership-small	4.55%	23.64%	23.64%	22.73%	25.45%
	employment	4.56%	29.97%	28.34%	16.29%	20.85%
	contract	4.23%	29.58%	26.06%	14.08%	26.06%
	non-active	0	26.83%	31.71%	14.63%	26.83%

Table 1 Legal Confidentiality Waivers of legal confidentiality granted by different entities - Lawyers' consent: An Analysis of Lawyer's Surveys (question: Who, according to you (lawyer), is entitled to waive legal confidentiality), (Response Rate, Most Frequent Responses Highlighted, Significant Demographic Characteristics), N = 782 people.

A poignant example of this stance is narrated by a legal adviser from Szczecin, who recounts an encounter with the prosecutor's office:

Once I had a client from Berlin, a businessman doing business in Poland and Germany. One day I received a letter from our prosecutor's office telling me to come to them. I come

to the prosecutor's office, and there the prosecutor, who I know, tells me that this client is involved in some petrol cases with extortion of VAT. She gives me a decision to waive my legal adviser privilege and asks me questions about my client's affairs. To this, I say to him: Whoa, whoa, I am not going to tell you anything, I am a legal adviser and I have a duty of confidentiality. She was very unhappy and threatened me that I would lose my licence to practice law. I complained to our court. There was a court hearing, there was a disciplinary ombudsman as my attorney, it took a long-time and... The court upheld the decision of the prosecutor's office. But after that, no one called me anyway. I would not have said anything about my client anyway. Confidentiality is confidentiality; I can always lose my memory, and if they were to give me a fine, I would already have made a deal with my client...

This account exemplifies the staunch commitment to confidentiality, even in the face of legal and professional threats. It highlights the tension between the duties of legal professionals and the powers of prosecutorial and executive authorities.

Figure 5 Legal Confidentiality Waivers Granted by Clients (question: Under what circumstances do you agree to the disclosure of legal confidentiality): Client's Survey Data (absolute indications, n=600 people).

The strong sentiments expressed by both clients and lawyers reflect a deep-seated mistrust in the executive branch's perceived overreach and oppressiveness. This mistrust, coupled with traditional opposition to authority and constant media reports of prosecutorial or police interference in private affairs, underscores the complexity and sensitivity surrounding the issue of confidentiality disclosure in the Polish legal system.

This scenario paints a vivid picture of the challenges and ethical dilemmas faced by legal professionals in navigating the landscape of legal confidentiality.

The Privatisation of Legal Confidentiality

Lawyers and clients in Poland share a common position on the disclosure of confidential information. Both groups are generally open to divulging matters protected by confidentiality if and only if the client consents. This consensus indicates a nuanced understanding of confidentiality, viewing it not merely as a rigid legal principle but as a flexible tool subject to the client's discretion.

However, the willingness to waive confidentiality is not absolute and is typically conditional. The notion that a lawyer can disclose confidential information upon the client's request does not imply an unrestricted freedom to do so. Instead, such a disclosure is often considered appropriate only in specific and justifiable circumstances. This selective acceptance underscores the delicate balance in the client-lawyer relationship, where the client's autonomy in confidentiality matters is paramount, potentially overshadowing the lawyer's professional judgment. A junior legal adviser from Katowice perceives the privatisation of legal confidentiality differently:

In my experience, there is an understanding with clients about handling legal confidentiality. We are open to discussing what is confidential, but it is always up to the client to give the green light. It is more than just sticking to the rules; it is about respecting the client's wishes. But, of course, it is not a free-for-all. Any disclosure has to make sense and be justified. In practice, it is a balance — what the client wants versus what is professionally appropriate. Their decision is crucial, but we always consider the bigger picture before going ahead.

Lawyers also express a willingness to abide by decisions made by their bar associations regarding confidentiality, particularly in situations involving conflicts, either between the client and the lawyer or among lawyers themselves, often relating to service payments. This deference to the judgment of the bar association reflects a professional respect for collective decision making in matters of ethical complexity.

At the core of these attitudes lies a deep-rooted mistrust in the justice system, authorities, and, to some extent, the legal profession itself. This mistrust fuels the perception of confidentiality not as an intrinsic cultural or ethical value, but rather as a

means to personal ends. As a result, there is a trend towards what can be described as the 'privatisation of legal confidentiality', where the control and use of confidential information are increasingly seen as a personal prerogative rather than a professional obligation.

This phenomenon reflects a significant shift in the way confidentiality is perceived and handled within the Polish legal system. It highlights the complex interplay between legal ethics, client autonomy, and social trust in legal institutions. This 'privatisation' underscores the evolving nature of legal practice in Poland, where traditional concepts of confidentiality are being reinterpreted and redefined in the modern legal landscape.

Future of legal confidentiality

The study has shed a revealing light on the intricate landscape of legal confidentiality in Poland, highlighting its status as a fundamental value within the realms of legal practice and culture. This value, as perceived by both lawyers and clients, is deeply ingrained, yet its interpretation and application are marked by notable discrepancies and shifting attitudes. These variances underscore the dynamic relationship between established legal norms, the ethical standards of the profession, and social views. A young lawyer from Częstochowa and Krakow shared the following opinion after reading the main research report on legal confidentiality:

This recent study really opens my eyes to how we handle legal confidentiality here in Poland. It is a big deal for us lawyers and our clients, deeply rooted in our legal culture. But you know, the way we interpret and apply it can vary a lot. There are these subtle differences and changing views that really show how dynamic our field is, balancing legal norms, ethical standards, and what society thinks.

What is clear is how important it is to keep the conversation going. We might need reforms or a better public understanding of how complex confidentiality can be. These findings? They are more than just a picture of where we are at now; they are a launchpad for future changes in how we think and work, not just in Poland but across Europe too. It is fascinating how these insights could shape legal practices and theories going forward.

This detailed exploration of confidentiality within the Polish legal framework underscores the imperative for continuous dialogue, the possibility of reforms, and the

cultivation of a deeper societal comprehension of confidentiality's complex nature. The findings of this study not only provide a snapshot of the current state of Polish legal practice, but also set the stage for future advancements in both legal theory and practice. These insights have implications that extend beyond national borders, resonate within the broader European legal context, and could influence future developments in this field.

Conclusions

The study of legal confidentiality in Poland not only underscores its enduring importance in the legal profession, but also provides nuanced answers to the stated goals and hypothesis. Our exploration reveals that while legal confidentiality remains a cornerstone of the legal system, its perception and application are subject to evolving attitudes and interpretations.

Key Findings and Implications

- (1) **Diversity and Complexity of Legal Confidentiality:** The study underscores the varied and intricate nature of legal confidentiality in Poland. This complexity often leads to confusion among lawyers and citizens alike and many struggling to fully grasp the different types of confidentiality, their application, and the legal methods for their revocation or suspension. Such confusion can result in inconsistent practices among legal professionals, particularly in times of legal change.
- (2) **Need for Enhanced Legal Education and Ethical Practice:** The findings call for better legal education and training to bridge knowledge gaps in regard to confidentiality. Lawyers should have a deeper understanding of the ethical and practical implications of their decisions about confidentiality.
- (3) **Challenges in Facilitating Public Authority Disclosure** The multitude of types of confidentiality complicates the ability of public authorities to disclose information, potentially affecting the essence of legal confidentiality. This situation calls for a careful balance act to uphold the sanctity of the client-lawyer relationship and the principle of justice.
- (4) **Omnipotence of Public Authorities and the Sanctity of Confidentiality:** In an era of increasing state omnipotence, the study highlights the ongoing struggle between public authorities and citizens, represented by their lawyers, over the issue of legal confidentiality (*Secrecy in Europe*, 2013; Winter et al.,

2020, pp. 105–395). This contention underscores the need for confidentiality to remain a steadfast pillar of Polish democracy.

- (5) **Unwavering Social and Legal Trust in Confidentiality:** Contrary to the notion that social and political changes or legal adjustments could alter the essence of confidentiality, our study finds that its fundamental importance remains unchanged. Legal confidentiality, as the cornerstone of democracy and justice, continues to be a crucial expectation among lawyers and citizens, serving as a bulwark against state overreach.

Study Objectives

The study confirms that both legal practitioners and clients regard confidentiality as essential. It is essential to ensure just and trustworthy interactions with authorities and to maintain the integrity of the legal profession. This finding aligns with our aim to understand the value placed on legal confidentiality in commercial legal practice, particularly among Polish legal advisers.

In addressing the conditions under which lawyers and clients consent to disclose confidential information, the study uncovers a cautious, yet flexible approach. Consent is typically given in specific, justifiable circumstances reflecting a measured balance between protecting client confidentiality and adhering to legal obligations.

Our investigation of the various types of confidentiality reveals a landscape marked by complexity and confusion. This aspect of the study highlights the need for greater clarity and education in understanding and differentiating between the various forms of confidentiality.

Research Hypothesis

The hypothesis posited that perceptions and attitudes towards legal confidentiality among lawyers, clients, and public authorities are evolving amidst dynamic legal landscapes. Our findings substantiate this hypothesis, indicating that, while the fundamental value of confidentiality remains unchanged, its practical application and social understanding are in flux. Contrary to the assumption that legal and social changes might alter the essence of confidentiality, our study demonstrates its steadfast role in Polish legal culture. However, the nuances in its application and understanding reflect a legal environment that responds to broader societal and legal changes.

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